

Could *Spathaspora* be a suitable partner for *Saccharomyces* in 2G-bioethanol production processes?

Raúl N. Comelli¹, Sofía Racca¹, Rodrigo Leonardi¹, Victoria Guzmán¹, Bruna C. Bolzico¹, Jorge Khawam¹, Tamara Llano² and Alberto Coz²

¹ Grupo de Procesos Biológicos en Ingeniería Ambiental (GPBIA).

Univ. Nacional del Litoral (UNL) – CONICET. Ciudad Universitaria, Santa Fe, Argentina

² Chemistry and Process & Resources Engineering Department. University of Cantabria, Santander, Spain

E-mail contact: rcomelli@fich.unl.edu.ar

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Abstract

Bioethanol stands out as a promising renewable biofuel, offering a potential solution to alleviate the environmental impact associated with fossil fuels when blended with gasoline. Second-generation (2G) bioethanol utilizes lignocellulosic agricultural waste, effectively minimizing land use pressure and reducing competition with food crops [1]. Despite the notable advantages it offers, lignocellulose brings forth several challenges, including the need for conditioning operations [2] and the lack of strains capable of efficiently fermenting pentoses, mainly D-xylose, and L-arabinose, which constitute 25-40% of total sugars. Due to the suboptimal performance of modified *Saccharomyces* strains, attention has shifted towards numerous native non-conventional yeasts with the capability to metabolize xylose [3].

This study aimed to assess the potential of selected non-conventional yeast strains for their integration with *Saccharomyces* in 2G-ethanol processes. Hence, a thorough analysis of the xylose consumption profile and ethanol production was carried out for several yeast strains utilizing kinetic and stoichiometric parameters. The strains were selected based on previously obtained results and comprised *Spathaspora passalidarum*, *Scheffersomyces stipitis*, *Pachysolen tannophilus*, *Kluyveromyces marxianus*, *Meyerozyma guilliermondii*, *Candida sp.*, *Yamadazima sp.*, and *Naganishia sp.* The presence of oxygen exerted a significant influence on xylose assimilation and fermentation. *Sp. passalidarum* showed the highest ethanol yields in non-aerated cultures. This strain displayed a preference for glucose over xylose, shifting to xylose utilization only after glucose depletion. The interruption of xylose fermentation with a glucose "pulse" effectively arrested xylose consumption, a trend observed with galactose but not with sucrose or fructose.

Optimal ethanol production was observed in the temperature range of 30-37°C, with pH values ranging from 4 to 7. *Sp. passalidarum* displayed sensitivity beyond 40 g/L ethanol, resulting in metabolic arrest. Finally, fermentations with glucose and xylose were conducted, employing various proportions of industrial *S. cerevisiae* var. Ethanol Red and *Sp. passalidarum*. Notably, both strains coexisted without competition, and their individual performances remained unaffected. Therefore, an interesting scenario arises: a process design based on mixed inocula, where *S. cerevisiae* leads the glucose consumption and *Sp. passalidarum* takes on the role of fermenting xylose once glucose has been depleted.

References

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